

Communication and alignment of expectations in implementing a PBL proposal

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5095564>

Abstract

Communication is a factor that can influence the success of projects, especially when several partners are involved and their joint action is necessary to achieve results. The implementation of a curricular change is one of those situations, because it is planned by curriculum managers, but will have as a final focus the work done by the students, who are the agents in the learning process and will make use of the experiences and strategies created for the curricula. Although the curricula are created based on the needs raised with students and teachers, their implementation requires a clear communication of objectives, teaching and assessment strategies, in addition to constant monitoring throughout the process, so that any adjustments can be made quickly, correcting the route in case of failures. This communication should ensure consensus on the purposes and engagement in the learning activities. Five years after the start of the implementation of a curricular proposal in an engineering school, which introduced the use of projects in parallel to the course subjects, two surveys were carried out, one with teachers and the other with students, and both showed the existence of doubts about the purpose of the changes introduced, which can be attributed to ineffective communication. The curricular change is consolidated and is valued by both teachers and students, however better results could have been achieved if there was better communication, which would make the experience more successful and, even, making the participants the best disseminators of this experience. This work analyses the communication aspects of this curriculum, based on the data from the two surveys, to identify problems and suggest actions.

Keywords: Project-based learning. Communication of the curriculum. Curricular change. Teacher conceptual change. Active learning strategies.

1 Introduction

The construction of a pedagogical project is something that arises from the moment that different demands contribute to its elaboration. Project Based Learning is a strategy that meets the demands for changing curricula in engineering courses. The change to these strategies is motivated by government agencies or by the universities themselves, to be aligned with employers, professional bodies, international influences, students, universities and governments, who with their policies coordinate the infrastructure to support engineering programs (Powell and Weenk, 2003).

The creation of a new curriculum is prepared by a team, considering the perception of everyone involved in the process, such as managers and teachers. Thus, the motivation and details of the new curriculum could be shared, making it a collective construction. In its implementation, when the curriculum is operationalized (Pacheco, 2005), the students join the various actors, and among them there must be clear, objective, efficient and effective communication so that adjustments can happen throughout this process. In the case of students, as they are the main elements of the learning process, the rules and agreements of the new curriculum must be made explicit in order to bring together all stakeholders and align training goals and expectations.

To discuss the issue of communication in the alignment of a curricular change, we will use the experience in an engineering school in which the team of teachers had the responsibility to create projects that promote the development of desirable competences to the students as: prepare them to interviews in a selection process, develop attitudes in a possible negotiation, be a leader on several occasions, among others, that meet the current National Curricular Guidelines - DCNs - for these engineering courses in Brazil (MEC, 2019).

This work emerged from the perception that the communication in the implementation of a curriculum was not adequate, and that the misalignment was perceived by teachers and students, which caused difficulties in the implementation of the curriculum proposal. Pointing out this type of problem can help in other types of experiences, promoting clear communication and with a better engagement of students, turn them more familiar with the new curriculum.

2 Theoretical References

The development of the curriculum involves procedures and, above all, people who collaborate and cooperate for its good implementation. Goodlad (1979) indicates that the curriculum goes through different levels with the 'ideal curriculum' being the beginning of the process, and ends with the "perceived curriculum", which is experienced in daily school activities. The perceived curriculum can be evaluated in surveys carried out with students and teachers after its implementation process. Thus, it is possible to identify possible gaps, as the communication between the interlocutors of this process - management, teachers and students.

The engineering programs in Brazil follow the National Curricular Guidelines (MEC, 2019) which orient undergraduate engineering programs in many dimensions. These guidelines indicate that engineering training aims to provide the future professional with several competences [12]. Among them, "Effective written, oral and graphic communication" stands out.

Communication is important to engineers because ask for to someone in a clear and objective way is the key to achieve what do you want. Likewise, knowing how to listen is the possibility of understanding the other and being able to directly offer what he wants. In addition, graphic expression, as an important part of communication, is fundamental for world modelling. Not to mention the ability to communicate using the voice, which in times of online activities has is very important, and is practiced in front of a computer screen. Thus, communication, whether oral, graphic or written, must be developed by engineering students.

The PBL integrates technical and transversal competencies to solve engineering problems and to fulfil the requirements imposed by professional contexts (Mesquita et al., 2013) and communication is one of those required competencies (Pascail, 2006; Lima et al., 2012). Silveira (2008) highlights some advantages that can be obtained with PBL, as "improves communication, organization, presentation, management, research, questioning, self-assessment, reflection, relationship skills and group leadership".

For all these reasons, good communication with students regarding the objectives of the projects used in the teaching-learning process, clarifying their contribution to the development of competences is the primary action to guarantee the development of communication skills (Mattasoglio Neto, et al., 2019).

3 Research method

This work uses part of the data from two surveys carried out with two different groups, one of professors and the other of students, both from the same engineering courses in which the projects were offered as complementary activities.

The data were obtained with questionnaires created in Google forms whose links were forwarded by email to each group. After then, they were worked in an Excel spreadsheet, which allowed the analysis of several dimensions, including communication. The questionnaires were sent to teachers and students from various courses at the school, and eight teachers and ninety-two students answered the questionnaire.

In the original research, different dimensions of analysis were considered with both teachers and students, and from these dimensions emerged the perception of the failure to communicate the curriculum goals to students, which is the focus of this work.

4 Findings

Data analysis and discussion are indicated in the items that follow.

4.1 Characterization of the samples

In the group of eight teachers five of them are male (62 %), and most are between 40 and 50 years old (75 %). All respondent teachers agree on the importance of using active strategies in learning, which are the ones that support the projects.

In the group of students, 41 % are male and 55 % are enrolled in daytime course, knowing that the school offers the courses at nocturnal again. The vast majority of respondent students are still students of the institution, as can be seen in the Table and at Table 2 it is observed that the different program in which the students are enrolled.

Table 1 – Series attended

Series	% of respondents
4 th annual period	35,0 %
5 th annual period	28,0 %
6 th annual period	27,0 %
Already concluded	10,0 %

Table 2 – Percentage of respondents by program

Program	% of respondents
Industrial Engineering	28,3 %
Chemistry	20,7 %
Civil	26,1 %
Electric	6,0 %
Food	14,1 %
Automation and control	4,3 %

4.2 The initial communication to presentation projects and expectation of projects

All teachers interviewed perceive the projects as generating improvements in the courses and 13 % identify that the projects are not directly linked to the technical content of engineering, but rather focused on the development of skills desired by the job market and related to behavioral aspects, soft skills.

For students, the projects met their initial expectations (80 %), but there is a need for adjustments to make them more aligned with these expectations (Figure). This indicates a small misalignment between what is communicated to students at the initial presentation of the projects and what is actually offered to them. Figure 2 shows that 75 % agree that the initial objectives have been met and 13 % disagree, what confirm this misalignment between the objectives presented and perceived by students.

Figure 1 – Expectation of students were achieved in the projects

Figure 2 – The objectives initially presented were achieved

4.3 Communication of projects on the point of view of teachers and students

Figure 3 brings the teachers' perceptions about the maturity of the students to realize the value of the projects in the curriculum. Along with this, 75 % of teachers have doubts that students understand the role of projects in the curriculum proposal. (Figure 4).

Figure 3 – By teachers, the students maturity to understand the importance of projects

Figure 4 – In the teachers views the student is aware of the objectives of the curriculum proposal implemented

To the teachers, the students do not realize the projects and the importance of active learning, which is the main strategy used and, in addition, they do not have knowledge about the implemented curriculum proposal. This leads to the perception that students only fulfill projects with the aim of achieving approval.

It was asked to students if there was good communication about the projects, 39 % said yes and 25 % said no, 36 % had doubts in the answer (Figure 5). When asked if they understood the real importance of the projects in the context of the course, which 73 % stated that they knew, 17 % had doubts and 10 % did not know the real purpose (Figure 6).

Figure 5 – To students - there was good communication about the projects with the students

Figure 6 – To students - Do you understand the purpose of the projects in the context of the course?

The perception that the projects were not properly communicated is explicit and points to the need for an action aimed specifically at promoting a clearer disclosure about the projects, their objectives and the strategies used in carrying out the activities. In a sample of 92 students and alumni, all experienced in the course, there is a high rate of those who indicate that the communication about the projects is poor and 10 % of the students do not realize their real importance in the context of the course.

There is a difference in responses between teachers and students. Teachers say that students have no clear perception of what the projects are, while students agree that they have a good understanding about the

purpose of the projects. Thus, there is a need for a more careful work of dissemination and alignment between the perception of students and teachers.

4.4 The communication factor as a competence

One of the objectives of the projects is to develop transversal skills, including communication, for a better performance in your future professional activity. When students were asked about the development of the communication competence in the projects (31 %), there is an indication that it is accomplished, and it is among the five most highlighted by the students. The others competences are: teamwork skills (45 %), solving problems (39 %), organizational and planning skills (35 %), creativity (31 %).

Although communication is valued as a competence by students, there is a failure in communication a part of teachers to conduct the curriculum. The students are not fully aware about what and how projects can contribute to their training. So, if a curriculum wants to teach communication, internal communication, especially with students, needs to be effective.

If attitudes are learned by experiencing, good communication in the school environment will promote the training of professionals who value these skills.

5 Conclusion

Although the communication in the initial phase led to the perception that the initial objectives and students' expectations were met, the perception between students and teachers regarding projects diverges.

The results indicate that, to the teachers, students do not recognize the true importance of projects and curricular change and are more concerned with having approval in the work performed instead of being perceived as learning opportunities for the development of skills.

From the research with the students, it can be concluded that the lack of communication is a factor that hinders the development of the projects because 75 % of the students think that there was no good communication and 27 % do not understand the real purpose of the projects.

Still regarding teachers, their commitment and sociability with the students are satisfactory. However, in the conduction of the projects and in the evaluations there are some flaws, which are not necessarily the fault of the teachers, but, as mentioned, it may be linked to the lack of communication.

It can be said that the perceived curriculum has not yet developed an identity in relation to the idealized curriculum, because there is a need of a better communication about the projects' objectives, clarifying their contribution to the development of competences.

6 Acknowledgments

To CNPq to support of scientific initiation scholarship. To the teachers and students who kindly collaborated in answering the survey.

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